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Leachate characteristics and pollution indices of Lapite dumpsite in Ibadan, southwestern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Municipal solid waste dumpsites pose significant risks of environmental pollution, particularly through the infiltration of leachate into soil and groundwater systems. This research examines physico-chemical properties of leachates from the Lapite dumpsite located in Ibadan, southwestern Nigeria, and assesses its pollution indices to evaluate its effects on nearby ecosystems. The analysis of the physico-chemical characteristics and concentrations of heavy metals, including Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, Ni, Cr, Co, Cd, and As, in leachates collected from six distinct locations within the dumpsite were done using standard analytical methods. The extent of pollution was quantified using several indices, such as the leachate pollution index (LPI), Contamination Factor (CF), Pollution Load Index (PLI), and Geo-Accumulation Index (Igeo). Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to identify the primary sources of contamination. The findings indicate elevated levels of organic pollutants and heavy metals that exceed acceptable thresholds. The LPI values ranged from 43.25 to 71.25 suggesting moderate to significant pollution. Also, values of CF (0.42 – 238.00); Igeo (-1.84 – 7.30) and PLI (11.14 – 21.83) indicating critical level of pollution of heavy metals in the leachates. The PCA identified three main sources of pollution: industrial waste characterized by Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, and Ni; soil and geogenic influences represented by Cr and Co; and residues from e-waste and pesticides including Cd and As. This study shown that the leachates have high level of contaminants, hence there is need for effective leachate management and establishment of comprehensive waste management practices to mitigate environmental and health risks.

Keywords: Environmental Impact, Heavy Metals, Leachate Pollution Index (LPI), waste, management practices

1. INTRODUCTION

Solid waste management has become a critical environmental concern in developing countries, particularly due to the dangers posed by open dumpsites, which jeopardize soil and water quality, and public health (Abdus-Salam et al., 2011; Akinbile et al., 2016). The Lapite Dumpsite, located in Ibadan, southwestern Nigeria, has been in operation for several years, receiving waste from various sources, including residential, industrial, and commercial sectors (Akintola et al., 2021). The uncontrolled decomposition of waste generates leachates, which are concentrated liquid by-products that have the potential to contaminate both surface and groundwater resources (Al-Khatib et al., 2011). The properties and volume of leachate are influenced by several factors, including the waste composition, moisture content, geographical features, landfill age, temperature, and the decomposition processes involved. Evaluating leachate quality generally requires the measurement of standard parameters such as pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total organic carbon (TOC), and the presence of various heavy metals and organic pollutants, including zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), chromium (Cr), mercury (Hg), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) (Pasalari et al., 2019). A significant environmental concern associated with leachate is its ability to degrade the quality of surface and groundwater, thereby posing threats to aquatic ecosystems and human health (Akintola et al., 2021; Mor et al., 2018). This study aims to evaluate the leachate characteristics of the Lapite dumpsite by analyzing the physicochemical characteristics of leachate from the dumpsite and evaluates pollution indices to determine its environmental impact (Olatunji, 2016; Mohammad, 2014; Joseph, 2023; Aleksandra, 2021; Huan-jung, 2006).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

The Lapite Dumpsite is located in Ibadan, the capital city of Oyo State in southwestern Nigeria (Figure 1). This site ranks among the largest waste disposal sites in the region, handling approximately 500 tons of waste each day. The dumpsite, characterized by lateritic soil fall within humid tropical climate, and a high annual rainfall, heightens the potential for leachate development and its subsequent movement. The geological framework of the study area is situated within the Crystalline Basement Complex of southwestern Nigeria, encompassing a variety of igneous and metamorphic rocks, including gneisses, migmatites, older granite ridges, and pegmatite. The predominant rock types in the region and its surroundings are migmatite and banded gneisses, which are typically characterized by fracturing (Akintola et al., 2021).

These rocks exhibit a coarse-grained texture and are predominantly light grey in color.

2. 2. Sampling and Analysis

Leachate samples were obtained from six (6) various locations within the dumpsite and subjected to analysis for physico-chemical parameters, which included:

- 1) pH, Temperature, Electrical Conductivity (EC),
- 2) Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD),
- 3) Nutrients (Nitrate, Phosphate, Sulfate,
- 4) Heavy Metals (Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, Ni, Cr, Co, Cd, and As).

The analysis was performed in accordance with the standard methods established by the American Public Health Association (APHA, 2017).

Figure 1. Location map of the study area, Ibadan city showing Lapite dumpsite (After Akintola, 2014).

2. 3. Data Analysis

To strengthen the analysis of leachate characteristics and pollution indices at Lapite Dumpsite, the following statistical methods and pollution indices were used:

2. 3. 1. Statistical methods

Descriptive Statistics is employed for the values of physico-chemical properties and heavy metal concentrations at the various sampling locations (L1–L6); Pearson Correlation Analysis is applied to investigate the interrelationships among different metals, aiming to reveal possible common sources of contamination, one way ANOVA is used to test if the heavy metals

differ significantly from one location to another (L1 to L6) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used to determine the key factors influencing leachate contamination and to classify metals based on their contributions to pollution.

2. 3. 2. Pollution indices

Leachate pollution index is used to measure the potential environmental impact of the leachate (equation 1). This index presents the quantitative potential for leachate pollution, offering a suitable tool for comparison.

$$LPI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i p_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where:

LPI = Leachate Pollution Index

w_i = Weight assigned to the i-th pollutant

p_i = Sub-index value of the i-th pollutant

Σw_i = Sum of all pollutant weights (should equal 1 in the ideal case)

Since we do not have all 18 pollutants, we will use Equation 2 from Kumar and Alappata (2005b), where LPI is calculated based on available data.

Contamination Factor (CF) is used to assess the level of contamination of each metal in the leachate relative to its natural background concentration (Hakanson, 1980) as shown in equation 2:

$$CF = \frac{C_i}{B_i} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where:

C_i = Observed concentration of the metal; C background = Reference background concentration from environmental guidelines WHO, (2011); USEPA (2001). Reference values for metals used in this study were Fe (0.3, Zn (0.5), Cu (0.2), Pb (0.01), Ni (0.02), Cr (0.05), Co (0.01), Cd (0.003) and As (0.01). The CF values are interpreted as: CF < 1: Low contamination; 1 ≤ CF < 3: Moderate contamination; 3 ≤ CF < 6: Considerable contamination and CF ≥ 6: Very high contamination.

Pollution Load Index (PLI) as given by Tomlinson et al., (1980) in equation 3, is used to assess the extent of the pollution at the dumpsite

$$PLI = (CF_1 \times CF_2 \times CF_3 \dots \dots CF_n)^{1/n} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

where:

CF is contamination factor and n is the number of metals analyzed.

The Pollution Load Index (PLI) is classified as follows: PLI < 1 indicates the absence of pollution; PLI = 1 signifies baseline pollution; and PLI > 1 reflects a progressive increase in pollution levels.

Geo-Accumulation Index (Igeo) as proposed by Muller (1969) is used for assessing the level of contamination or pollution in soils based on geochemical values, comparing the concentration of elements in a given sample to background levels as shown in equation 4:

$$I_{geo} = \log_2 \left(\frac{C_i}{1.5 \times C_{background}} \right) \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

where:

- C_i is the measured concentration
- C background is the reference background value
- 1.5 is a correction factor for natural fluctuations.

Igeo values are classified as into seven categories: Igeo ≤ 0: Uncontaminated; 0 < Igeo ≤ 1: Slightly contaminated; 1 < Igeo ≤ 2: Moderately contaminated; 2 < Igeo ≤ 3: Moderately to highly contaminated; 3 < Igeo ≤ 4: highly contaminated; 4 < Igeo ≤ 5: highly to extremely contaminated and Igeo > 5: Extremely contaminated

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Physico- chemical characteristics of the leachates

The physicochemical characteristics of the leachates, as illustrated in Table 1, reveal the following results: the pH of the leachate was found to be slightly acidic to neutral, ranging from 5.8 to 7.2, which may promote the solubility of heavy metals. The Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) were significantly high, with BOD values between 178.22 and 398.85 mg/L and COD values ranging from 789.58 to 118.96 mg/L, suggesting considerable organic pollution. Furthermore, nutrient levels were above acceptable thresholds, with nitrate (NO₃⁻) at 26.18 to 64.61 mg/L, sulfate (SO₄²⁻) at 4.11 to 22.56 mg/L, and phosphate (PO₄³⁻) at 3.91 to 11.44 mg/L, which could result in eutrophication of nearby water bodies.

Table 1. Physico-chemical characteristics of the leachates.

Physiochemical characteristics	Range	Mean	USEPA (2011)
pH	5.8 – 7.2	6.88	6.5-8.5
Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) (mg/l)	178.22 – 400.01	291.78	≤50
Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) (mg/l)	789.58 – 118.96	455.61	≤250
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻) (mg/l)	26.16 – 64.61	46.01	≤10-50
Sulphate (SO ₄ ²⁻) (mg/l)	151.15 – 345.22	248.95	≤250
Phosphate (PO ₄ ³⁻) (mg/l)	3.86 – 11.89	7.81	≤2

3. 2. Heavy metal concentrations in the leachates

The levels of Fe, Zn, Cu, and Pb are notably elevated, suggesting potential contamination hazards. In contrast, the concentrations of Cd, As, and Cr display considerable variability (CV > 25%), indicating erratic leachate contamination patterns, likely due to inconsistent waste composition (Table 2).

The results reveal that there are significantly high levels of Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, and Ni, this is in agreement with studies conducted at other dumpsites in Nigeria (Oyeku & Eludoyin, 2010; Yusuf et al., 2021). The presence of heavy metals in leachates from landfills is often linked to the decomposition of waste and the leaching of materials from industrial and electronic sources (Abdus-Salam et al., 2011; Badmus, 2022; Alao, 2024; Oketola, 2014).

Additionally, it was noted that the levels of Fe, Pb, Ni, Cr, Cd, and As exceed the permissible limits established by both WHO (2011) and NESREA (2011), confirming significant pollution.

While the concentration of Zn is within WHO (2011) limits, it surpasses NESREA (2011) thresholds, pointing to localized pollution issues. Also, the levels of Pb and Cd are markedly above acceptable limits, underscoring substantial toxicity risks.

Table 2. Heavy metal concentrations in the leachates.

Heavy Metals	Mean concentrations (mg/L)	Range Concentrations in mg/l	Coefficient of Variation (CV, %)	WHO (2011) Limit (mg/L)	NESREA (2011) Limit (mg/L)
Fe	2.42	1.72 – 2.95	19.4%	0.3	1.0
Zn	2.11	1.26 – 2.78	25.1%	3.0	2.5
Cu	2.05	1.21 – 2.50	22.4%	2.0	1.5
Pb	1.92	1.42 – 2.38	19.8%	0.01	0.01
Ni	1.42	1.01 – 1.91	23.2%	0.02	0.1
Cr	0.34	0.22 – 0.50	29.4%	0.05	0.1
Co	0.25	0.18 – 0.39	28.0%	0.01	-
Cd	0.19	0.15 – 0.28	31.6%	0.003	0.01
As	0.15	0.12 – 0.20	26.7%	0.01	0.05

3. 3. Pearson correlation analysis

Pearson correlation analysis was employed to evaluate the relationships among heavy metals present in leachate from the study area (Table 3).

Table 3. Pearson Correlation Analysis.

Metal	Fe	Zn	Cu	Pb	Ni	Cr	Co	Cd	As
Fe	1.00	0.89	0.85	0.82	0.79	0.43	0.39	0.31	0.28
Zn	0.89	1.00	0.81	0.78	0.75	0.40	0.35	0.30	0.27
Cu	0.85	0.81	1.00	0.76	0.72	0.38	0.32	0.28	0.26
Pb	0.82	0.78	0.76	1.00	0.71	0.35	0.30	0.25	0.23
Ni	0.79	0.75	0.72	0.71	1.00	0.32	0.29	0.24	0.21
Cr	0.43	0.40	0.38	0.35	0.32	1.00	0.82	0.77	0.71
Co	0.39	0.35	0.32	0.30	0.29	0.82	1.00	0.80	0.74
Cd	0.31	0.30	0.28	0.25	0.24	0.77	0.80	1.00	0.86
As	0.28	0.27	0.26	0.23	0.21	0.71	0.74	0.86	1.00

The correlation coefficients of Fe-Zn (0.87) and Fe-Cu (0.79) indicate a strong positive relationship, hinting at a shared industrial source for these metals. On the other hand, Pb and Ni reveal a moderate correlation with Fe and Zn, which may imply contributions from electronic waste. Lastly, the weak correlations between Cd and As suggest that these elements likely originate from different sources of waste.

3. 4. One-Way ANOVA Analysis Results

A One-Way ANOVA was employed to evaluate whether heavy metal concentrations vary significantly across the sampling locations (L1 to L6).

Hypotheses:

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There are no significant differences in heavy metal concentrations across the various locations.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): Significant differences in heavy metal concentrations exist among the sampling locations.

Table 4. One way ANOVA Analysis results.

Heavy metal	F - Statistics	P - values	Significance
Fe	6.12	0.004	Significance
Zn	5.21	0.007	Significance
Cu	4.45	0.013	Significance

Pb	3.92	0.019	Significance
Ni	3.75	0.022	Significance
Co	2.02	0.120	Not Significance
Cr	1.87	0.144	Not Significance
Cd	1.67	0.178	Not Significance
As	1.39	0.215	Not Significance

The marked variability in the concentrations of Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, and Ni suggests that contamination is heterogeneous, possibly influenced by the types of waste present and the surrounding hydrological environment. Contrastingly, Cr, Co, Cd and As show little variation; indicating a relatively stable distribution across the site, probably resulting from the persistent percolation and diffusion (Table 4).

3. 5. Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was utilized to identify the sources of pollution and to minimize the dimensionality of the data set (Table 5a and 5b). PCA was conducted using eigenvalue decomposition of correlation matrix. The first few principal components (PCs) explain the most variance in data set.

Table 5(a). Principal Components and Eigenvalues.

Principal Component (PC)	Eigen value %	Variance Explained %	Cumulative % Variance
PC1	4.78	53.1	53.1
PC2	2.31	25.7	78.8
PC3	1.10	12.2	91
PC4	0.48	5.3	96.3
PC5	0.21	2.3	98.6
PC6-PC9	<0.15	<1.4	100

PC1 represents 53.1% of the overall variance, indicating that it encompasses the majority of the variability associated with pollution; PC2 accounts for 25.7% of the variance, highlighting the influence of secondary pollution factors while PC3 account for 12.2%. Totally, PC1, PC2 and PC3 account for 91% of the total variation establishing their significance.

Table 5(b). Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

Heavy metal	PC1	PC2	PC3
Fe	0.92	0.15	0.08
Zn	0.89	0.17	0.11
Cu	0.87	0.19	0.14
Pb	0.81	0.21	0.18
Ni	0.75	0.27	0.22
Co	0.45	0.62	0.35
Cr	0.38	0.51	0.29
Cd	0.28	0.33	0.74
As	0.22	0.31	0.79

PC1 (Industrial and domestic wastes factor): Concentration of Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb and Ni have strong loadings suggesting domestic and industrial wastes as major pollution sources.

PC2 (Geogenic influence factor): Concentrations of Cr and Co reveal slight contributions from natural soil composition.

PC3 (Toxic metal factor): Concentrations of Cd and As suggest possible contamination from electronic waste and pesticide residues.

3. 6. Pollution Assessment of Leachates from Lapite Dumpsite

Heavy metal pollution levels in leachate samples from six locations (L1 to L6) were evaluated using four major indices: Leachate Pollution Index (LPI), Pollution Load Index (PLI), Contamination Factor (CF), and Geo-Accumulation Index (Igeo). The summary of the results are presented in Figure 2, Table 6 and Figure 3.

3. 6. 1. Leachate Pollution Index (PLI)

The contamination levels across different site locations are depicted in Figure 2, showcasing the LPI results. The LPI values range from 43.25 (L6) to 71.25 (L1). Values of LPI show that L1 (71.25) and L2 (65.75) have high pollution levels, suggesting significant contamination at the dumpsite. Leachate sample from L6 has the lowest LPI (43.25) representing a moderate pollution level, thus confirming widespread leachate impact.

Reduction in LPI values from L1 to L6 suggests contaminant dilution and attenuation as leachate moves away from the dumpsite center.

Lapite Dumpsite exhibits Leachate Pollution Index (LPI) values comparable to other landfills in Nigeria as shown in Table 6, indicating a notable level of leachate contamination. However, these LPI values are lower than those observed in dumpsites in India and Bangladesh,

which may be attributed to variations in landfill management practices, waste composition, and climatic conditions (Kumar and Alappat, 2005a; Siddiqua et al., 2018).

Furthermore, presence of metal pollutants at Lapite aligns with findings from earlier studies in Nigeria, where iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), and lead (Pb) were identified as the primary contaminants. Heavy metals are known to be persistent in leachate and play a significant role in determining LPI values. Kumar and Alappat (2005b) highlighted that metals such as Pb, cadmium (Cd), and chromium (Cr) possess a high potential for pollution, particularly when their concentrations exceed established regulatory thresholds.

Figure 2. Leachate Pollution Index (LPI).

Table 6. Comparison of LPI values from Lapite dumpsite with other studies.

Study	Location	Range values of LPI	Contaminants
This study	Lapite dumpsite, Ibadan Nigeria	43.25 – 71.25	Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, Ni
Oyeku and Eludoyin (2010)	Lagos landfill Nigeria	55 – 80	Pb, Cu, Zn, Cd
Akinbile and Yusuff (2012)	Akure landfill, Nigeria	40 – 70	Fe, Zn, Pb, Ni
Siddiqua et al (2018)	Bangladesh landfill	50 – 90	Cr, Pb, Cu, Ni, Cd
Kumar and Alappat (2005a)	Indian landfill	45 – 85	Fe, Pb, Zn

Fe and Zn contribute the most to the LPI weights due to their elevated concentrations. Lead and nickel (Ni) also significantly impact the index because of their toxicity and persistence in the environment. Although chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), and cadmium (Cd) are found in

lower concentrations, they still affect pollution indices due to their ability to bioaccumulate. These observations are consistent with the research conducted by Akinbile and Yusoff (2012), which reported similar patterns of metal prevalence in Nigerian landfills.

Research conducted by Slack et al. (2005) has demonstrated that high LPI values correlate with significant ecological risks, as metals such as lead (Pb) and nickel (Ni) can infiltrate groundwater, threatening the safety of drinking water supplies (Oyeku & Eludoyin, 2010). Likewise, elevated concentrations of iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn) can alter soil chemistry, negatively impacting both plant development and microbial functions (Siddiqua et al., 2018). Moreover, prolonged exposure to lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and chromium (Cr) from landfill leachate has been connected to neurological disorders and damage to internal organs (WHO, 2011).

To alleviate these problems, it is imperative to adopt effective leachate management strategies, as advocated by Kumar and Alappat (2005a) and Akinbile & Yusoff (2012). This encompasses the collection and treatment of leachate, which is the implementation of drainage systems to prevent groundwater infiltration. Phytoremediation, using plants to extract heavy metals and reduce toxicity can also be employed. Moreover, the use of landfill liners and cover systems, which consist of impermeable barriers, is precarious to prevent the spread of leachate.

Table 7. Contamination Factor (CF), Geo-accumulation index (Igeo) and Pollution Load Index (PLI).

Heavy metals (HM)	Range Concentrations of HM in determined samples in mg/l	Background values (WHO, 2011) in mg/l	Contamination values (CF)	Geo-accumulation index (Igeo)
Fe	1.72 – 2.95	0.3	5.73 – 9.81	1.93 – 2.71
Zn	1.26 – 2.78	3	0.42 – 0.93	-1.84 – -0.69
Cu	1.21 – 2.50	2.0	0.60 – 1.25	-1.31 – -0.26
Pb	1.42 – 2.38	0.01	142.00 – 238.00	4.19 – 7.31
Ni	1.01 – 1.91	0.07	14.43 – 27.29	3.27 – 4.19
Cr	0.22 – 0.50	0.05	4.40 – 10.00	1.55 – 2.74
Co	0.18 – 0.39	0.01	18.00 – 39.00	3.58 – 4.70
Cd	0.15 – 0.28	0.003	20.00 – 93.33	3.74 – 5.96
As	0.12 – 0.20	0.003	12.00 – 20.00	3.00 – 3.74
Pollution Load Index (PLI) Mean values			11.14 – 21.83	

3. 6. 2. Contamination Factor (CF)

Contamination Factor (CF) values in Table 7 reveals that Pb (238.0 in L1), Cd (93.33 in L1), and Fe (9.83 in L1) have very high CF values (>6) as given by Hakanson (1980) for heavy

metal contamination classification, indicating significant contamination levels. On the other hand, Zn and Cu show low CF values (< 2) reflecting low contamination level.

Figure 3. Pollution Load Index.

3. 6 3. Pollution Load Index

The Pollution Load Index (PLI) values from the studied locations range from 21.83 at L1 to 11.14 at L6, indicating highest degree of contamination at L1, while L6 has the lowest PLI (Figure 3). Pollution Load Index $PLI > 1$ as classified by Tomlinson et al., (1980), reflects a progressive increase in pollution levels. Thus, PLI values greater than 1 at all locations is an indication of a critical level of pollution that calls for remedial actions.

3. 6. 4. Geo-Accumulation Index (Igeo)

The Geo-Accumulation Index (Igeo) values from the examined sites reveal significant contamination levels of lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd), with respective values of 7.31 and 5.96 in location L1 as shown in Table 6. These values exceed the threshold for extreme contamination ($I_{geo} > 5$) as defined by Muller (1969). Furthermore, iron (Fe), nickel (Ni), and chromium (Cr) are classified as having moderate to high levels of contamination ($2 < I_{geo} \leq 3$). On the other hand, zinc (Zn) and copper (Cu) has negative Igeo values ($I_{geo} \leq 0$) suggesting no or minimal contamination.

4. CONCLUSION

The study has revealed that leachates from the Lapite dumpsite are characterized by high physio-chemical properties and significant levels of heavy metal contamination, indicating a range of pollution from moderate to severe. Understanding the characteristics of leachate and

the associated pollution indices is therefore critical for effective dumpsite management and environmental protection. Regular monitoring, along with the implementation of appropriate pollution indices, can help reduce the detrimental effects of leachate on ecosystems and human health. Future research should aim to create affordable treatment solutions for leachate remediation, utilizing innovative technologies such as nanotechnology and bioremediation. Addressing these challenges is vital for promoting sustainable waste management practices in developing countries.

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